

Poster Abstracts: All-Island Cancer Data Forum

26th and 27th January 2026, Riddel Hall, Queen's University Belfast

1. **surviveR: A flexible shiny application for patient survival analysis**

Tamas Sessler, Gerard Quinn, Mark Wapett, Emily Rogan, David Sharkey, Baharak Ahmaderaghi, Mark Lawler, Daniel Longley, Simon McDade

2. **Standardization of Irish Prostate Cancer Data Using OMOP CDM for ML-Based PI-RADS 3 Biopsy Decision Support**

Jeremiah Akintomide¹, Amirhossein Jalali¹, William Watson², Katie Crowley¹

3. **Standardising the Irish Prostate Cancer Outcomes Registry Using the OMOP Common Data Model: Enabling High-Quality, National-Scale Cancer Outcomes Research**

Muhammad Mohsin Memon¹, Jeremiah Akintomide², Linh Hoang¹, Wasfa Farooq¹, David Galvin¹, Katie Crowley², William Watson¹

4. **Building a Federated, FAIR-Compliant Clinico-Genomic Data Framework for Acute Myeloid Leukaemia in Ireland**

David Akwuru¹, Katie Crowley¹, Nina Orfali², Aedin Culhane¹

5. **Connecting Clinical and Molecular Data for Lymphoid Blood Cancers: All-Island Federated Learning Approach**

Amanda Kowalczyk^{1,2}, Kluivert Boakye Duah^{1,2}, Chinaemerem Anthony Daraibeau¹, Ruth Clifford^{3,4,2}, Ian Overton^{1,5}

6. **Building a framework for harmonization of blood cancer data and federated research across Ireland**

Marina Ainciburu¹, Kemdil Anyaoku¹, Peter Doyle², Wei Jan Chang³, David Akwuru¹, Kluivert Boakye Duah⁴, Amanda Kowalczyk⁴, Divya Soni⁵, Brian Hayes², Alanna McMullin², Mary Cahill², Rachel Brodie², Eva Szegezdi⁵, Ian Overton⁴, Katie Crowley¹, Leonie Young³, Siobhan Glavey³, Nina Orfali⁶, Mark Lawler⁷, Aedin Culhane¹, Ruth Clifford⁸

7. **Standardisation and Quality Control of Irish Lymphoid Blood Cancers Data with the OMOP CDM and eHDPRep**

Kluivert Boakye Duah¹²³, Amanda Kowalczyk¹², Kemdil Anyaoku², Aedin C. Culhane²⁴, Mark Lawler¹²³, Siobhan Glavey²⁵⁶, Ruth Clifford²⁴⁷, Ian M. Overton¹²³

8. **Evolutionary Insights into the B7 Immune Checkpoint Family and Their Implications for Tissue-Specific Immunotherapy Response.**

Dibyaswarupa Mohanty, Aedin C. Culhane

9. **Estimating the Patient Population in Ireland for Each Molecularly-Guided Oncology Therapy Approved by the European Medicines Agency: A Paediatric Perspective**

G. O'Mahoney¹, B. Reardon^{1,2}, C. Haugh³ and A. Culhane¹

10. **Genomic Evidence for Depolyploidization as a Stabilising Force in post-WGD Cancers**

Evie M. Smyth¹, Elle Loughrin¹, Aliah Hawari², Christopher Wirth², Maria Jakobsdottir³, David C. Wedge², Máire Ní Leathlobhair¹

11. **Concurrent endometrial cancer in patients with an index endometrial hyperplasia diagnosis: a population-based study**

Chloe McCoy¹, Helen Coleman¹, Charlene McShane¹, Finian Bannon¹, Omolara Sanni², W Glenn McCluggage³, James Wylie⁴, Declan Quinn⁴, Damien Bennett⁵, Úna McMenamin¹

12. Endometrial cancer and prior diagnosis of endometrial hyperplasia: a population-based study

Chloe McCoy¹, Helen Coleman¹, Charlene McShane¹, Finian Bannon¹, Omolara Sanni², W Glenn McCluggage³, Declan Quinn⁴, James Wylie⁴, Anna Gavin⁵, Damien Bennett⁵, Úna McMenamin¹

13. The incidence of endometrial hyperplasia in Northern Ireland: A population-based study

Lauren McKenna¹, Haydee Jordao¹, Omolara Sanni², Chloe McCoy¹, W Glenn McCluggage³, James Wylie⁴, Declan Quinn⁴, Anna Gavin⁵, Damien Bennett⁵, Helen Coleman⁵, Christopher Cardwell¹, Úna McMenamin¹

14. Stage at diagnosis and breast cancer-specific mortality in breast cancer patients treated with antidepressants, anxiolytics, and antipsychotics: A population-based cohort study from Northern Ireland.

Sarah Baxter¹, Charlene M. McShane¹, Stuart A. McIntosh^{1,2}, Damien Bennett^{3,1}, Lynne Lohfeld¹, Daniel R.S. Middleton¹, Gerard Savage³, Deirdre Fitzpatrick³, Joseph Kane^{1,4}, Ann McBrien⁵, David McCallion⁶, Anna Gavin¹, Chris R. Cardwell¹

15. House value as an individual socioeconomic indicator for breast cancer survival and late-stage diagnosis: a population-based cohort study from Northern Ireland

Sarah Baxter¹, Charlene M. McShane¹, Stuart A. McIntosh^{1,2}, Damien Bennett^{3,1}, Meenakshi Sharma¹, Lynne Lohfeld¹, Daniel R.S. Middleton¹, Gerard Savage³, Deirdre Fitzpatrick³, Ann McBrien⁴, David McCallion⁵, Anna Gavin¹, Chris R. Cardwell¹

16. CRUK Cancer Data Driven Detection (CD3) Programme

Lara Edwards¹, Antonis Antoniou², Sunil Dolwani³, Ashley Akbari⁴, Montse Garcia-Closas⁵

17. ELIXIR-Ireland and Bioconductor: Opportunities for Irish Genomics Research

Maria Doyle, Gavin Farrell, Aedín Culhane

18. eHealth-Hub for Cancer: A Cancer Data Network on the Island of Ireland eHealth-Hub for Cancer Consortium

David Akwuru^{1,3*}, Kluivert Boakye Duah^{5*}, Arya Soman^{1,4*}, Brendan Reardon^{1,11*}, DibyaSwarupa Mohanty^{1*}, Jeremiah Akintomide^{1,3*}, Abhishek^{1*}, EthnaMcFerran⁵, Ruth Clifford^{1,2}, Katie Crowley^{1,3}, Shirin Moghaddam^{1,4}, William Waston⁶, Clare Donohoe¹⁰, Nina Orfali¹⁰, Eva Szegezdi⁷, Siobhan Galvey⁸, Mary Cahill⁹, Amir Jalali¹, Michael Quinn⁵, Ian Overton⁵, Simon McDade⁵, Mark Lawler⁵, Aedin C. Culhane¹

1. **surviveR: A flexible shiny application for patient survival analysis**

Tamas Sessler, Gerard Quinn, Mark Wapett, Emily Rogan, David Sharkey, Baharak Ahmaderaghi, Mark Lawler, Daniel Longley, Simon McDade

Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

The increasing volume and diversity of genomic, molecular, and phenotypic data in biomedical research present major opportunities — but also significant challenges — for patient survival analysis. Traditional commercial graphing/statistical packages often lack the flexibility to handle complex cohort definitions, while open-source tools typically demand substantial computational expertise, putting them out of reach for many researchers. We present **surviveR**, a cloud-based, user-friendly web application built with the Shiny framework, designed to make survival analysis accessible for researchers without advanced computational backgrounds. surviveR enables intuitive data upload, flexible cohort filtering, and dynamic subgrouping on categorical or discretized continuous variables (e.g., gene expression, protein levels), followed by automatic generation of Kaplan–Meier survival curves, log-rank tests, and Cox proportional-hazard regression (hazard ratios and confidence intervals). We demonstrate its utility via application to a clinically relevant colorectal cancer cohort, successfully integrating clinical, transcriptomic, and immunohistochemical data to reveal prognostic insights. By combining ease-of-use with advanced statistical capabilities, surviveR empowers non-expert users to perform robust, custom survival analyses — lowering the barrier to extracting biologically meaningful survival associations from complex multi-omic datasets.

2. Standardization of Irish Prostate Cancer Data Using OMOP CDM for ML-Based PI-RADS 3 Biopsy Decision Support

Jeremiah Akintomide¹, Amirhossein Jalali¹, William Watson², Katie Crowley¹

¹University of Limerick, Limerick, Ireland. ²University College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

Background: Men with PI-RADS 3 prostate MRI lesions face a "diagnostic grey zone," leading to significant rates of unnecessary biopsies. Our preliminary analysis of the Irish Prostate Cancer Outcomes Research (IPCOR) registry (n=94) indicates that PI-RADS 3 lesions account for ~50% of biopsies, yet 50% of these are benign. To address this, we aim to develop a Machine Learning (ML) risk-stratification tool. However, the prerequisite is transforming the heterogeneous registry data into a standardized, interoperable format: the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM).

Methods & Progress: This study employs a mixed-methods approach. We established a robust governance framework, securing multi-institutional ethics approvals and a legal collaborative agreement. A technical proof-of-concept ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) pipeline was built and validated using synthetic data (Synthea). Crucially, an on-site landscape analysis was conducted at a major hospital site to map real-world data collection workflows.

Results: The landscape analysis identified a critical "ontological gap" where source data exists as non-coded text strings rather than standardized concepts, necessitating a novel "ontological enrichment" methodology. We also co-developed open-source tooling (omop-vocabulary-downloader) to streamline CDM deployment, achieving over 10,000 downloads.

Conclusion: This project establishes the technical and semantic foundation for transforming a national cancer registry into a high-quality, research-ready asset. By standardizing real-world data, we enable the development of interoperable AI/ML tools to optimize biopsy decision-making for Irish patients.

3. Standardising the Irish Prostate Cancer Outcomes Registry Using the OMOP Common Data Model: Enabling High-Quality, National-Scale Cancer Outcomes Research

Muhammad Mohsin Memon¹, Jeremiah Akintomide², Linh Hoang¹, Wasfa Farooq¹, David Galvin¹, Katie Crowley², William Watson¹

¹UCD School of Medicine and Conway Institute, UCD, Dublin, Ireland

²Department of Computer Science and Information Systems and Health Research Institute, University of Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

The Irish Prostate Cancer Outcomes Research (IPCOR) research team has created a prostate cancer clinical quality registry designed to answer policy and research questions regarding prostate cancer diagnosis, treatment, and the impacts of treatment. IPCOR systematically collects diagnostics, treatment, biospecimens, and Patient-Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) across multiple sites. While the registry provides a national data asset, the dataset currently exists in a non-standardised form, limiting interoperability, cross-site comparability, and advanced analytics.

This project aims to transform IPCOR data by mapping it into the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM). OMOP standardisation offers a unified, ontology-driven framework that enables interoperability, federated analysis, and reproducibility of large-scale research, using standard vocabularies such as SNOMED CT. As part of the eHealth-Hub All-Island Research Hub for Federated Analysis of Cancer Data, this work will develop the ETL pipelines and ontological mappings, and data quality workflows necessary to convert IPCOR into a harmonised OMOP dataset.

Embedding the standardisation process allows the examination of key operational challenges: manual extraction from unstructured records, PROM-dependent variables, data missingness, and the lack of a national patient identifier. The resulting OMOP-compatible registry will strengthen quality improvement, benchmarking, and population-level outcomes research and support future innovations such as machine-learning risk prediction tools for clinically ambiguous PI-RADS 3 cases.

Ultimately, this work enables the IPCOR registry as an interoperable cancer data resource and demonstrates how OMOP CDM can strengthen cancer outcomes research, clinical decision support systems, and evidence-based improvements in prostate cancer care in Ireland.

4. Building a Federated, FAIR-Compliant Clinico-Genomic Data Framework for Acute Myeloid Leukaemia in Ireland

David Akwuru¹, Katie Crowley¹, Nina Orfali², Aedin Culhane¹

¹University of Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

²St. James's Hospital, Dublin, Ireland

Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML) poses a significant challenge in Ireland, with over 130 annual diagnoses and a 5-year survival rate of approximately 20%. As the population ages, the burden on the healthcare system is estimated to rise, yet progress is hindered by a fragmented data landscape where clinical and genomic data remain siloed. This study aims to develop a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) federated clinico-genomic data platform to enable scalable, all-island precision oncology research while preserving data privacy.

We conducted a landscape analysis across five hospitals in Ireland to evaluate governance and data-sharing barriers, alongside a JBI-aligned scoping review of international practices and standards. Following this, we developed a robust Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) pipeline using Python and DBT to map both synthetic AML data (generated from Synthea) and the de-identified MIMIC IV dataset to OMOP CDM. The ETL process was refined to include genomic fields from studies utilizing generative AI to simulate clinical trials. Cohorts were characterised in ATLAS using SNOMED-CT, and secure federated analytics platforms (DataSHIELD, Vantage6) were assessed for feasibility.

The landscape analysis revealed significant heterogeneity in data collection and governance across hospital sites. The ETL pipeline successfully standardised both clinical and genomic synthetic data to the OMOP CDM with >95% conformance rates, enabling efficient characterization of AML cohorts.

This work delivers a FAIR-aligned, all-island federated infrastructure for clinico-genomic AML research. By demonstrating technical feasibility with synthetic and MIMIC datasets, we provide a scalable blueprint for federated cancer research.

5. Connecting Clinical and Molecular Data for Lymphoid Blood Cancers: All-Island Federated Learning Approach

Amanda Kowalczyk^{1,2}, Kluivert Boakye Duah^{1,2}, Chinaemerem Anthony Daraibeau¹, Ruth Clifford^{3,4,2}, Ian Overton^{1,5}

¹The Johnston Cancer Research Centre, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

²eHealth-Hub for Cancer, Limerick, Ireland

³University of Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

⁴University Hospital Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

⁵eHealth-Hub for Cancer, Belfast, Ireland

Cancer is the leading cause of death on the island of Ireland. A standard approach in data analysis involves holding the data at a centralised location. Accordingly different sites may send their data to the host (the entity performing the analysis). This introduces a single point of vulnerability for breaches and raises serious ethical and legal questions about patient privacy, data ownership, and issues with data standardisation and interoperability.

Decentralised data federation can address privacy issues for data sharing, where models are sent to the data. Sub-queries and analyses are carried out locally at each site and are sent securely to central server, by using Personal Health Train framework together with OMOP Common Data Model that allows interoperability across different sites.

The eHealth-Hub will bring cross-border real-world health research that will inform evidence-based policy to improve cancer patient survival and enable real-time data access to support cross-border health and social care partnerships. This can be achieved by deploying infrastructure that would allow federated learning across multiples sites in Ireland and Northern Ireland.

We successfully deployed a federated learning network locally at QUB by using vantage6 infrastructure. As a proof of principle, we are building a network where we can safely assess and demonstrate feasibility while conducting risk assessments using synthetic data to ensure its compliant with the international standards for information security (ISO 27001). We plan to use federated learning to illuminate correlates of blood cancer progression by analysing lymphoid blood cancer datasets from sites in Ireland and Northern Ireland.

6. Building a framework for harmonization of blood cancer data and federated research across Ireland

Marina Ainciburu¹, Kemdil Anyaoku¹, Peter Doyle², Wei Jan Chang³, David Akwuru¹, Kluivert Boakye Duah⁴, Amanda Kowalczyk⁴, Divya Soni⁵, Brian Hayes², Alanna McMullin², Mary Cahill², Rachel Brodie², Eva Szegezdi⁵, Ian Overton⁴, Katie Crowley¹, Leonie Young³, Siobhan Glavey³, Nina Orfali⁶, Mark Lawler⁷, Aedin Culhane¹, Ruth Clifford⁸

¹University Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

²Cork University Hospital, Cork, Ireland

³Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, Dublin, Ireland

⁴Queens University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁵University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

⁶St James Hospital, Dublin, Ireland

⁷Queens University Belfast, Belfast, Ireland

⁸University Hospital Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

Cancer research needs collaborative studies that generate real world evidence (RWE) to supplement clinical trial data and influence drug approval and reimbursement policies. Currently, clinical cancer data is heterogenous among hospitals on the island of Ireland, in different electronic clinical records systems and other paper-based sources, many of which are unconnected between hospitals. Data harmonization across sites is a challenging task.

As part of the eHealth-Hub for Cancer, we aim to standardize data from patients with blood cancer in hospitals across the island of Ireland, to make it usable for RWE studies. As a proof of concept, patient data from three types of blood cancer with distinctive characteristics: chronic lymphocytic leukaemia (CLL), multiple myeloma (MM) and acute myeloid leukaemia (AML) were prioritized for data harmonization using the OMOP-CDM.

We first established a set of variables to be collected for each of the cancer types, which enable the study of clinically relevant questions. We defined three data dictionaries that include 180-200 variables each, collected in 20 tables covering demographics, clinical history, diagnostic and laboratory testing (radiology, biochemistry, immunophenotyping, genomics...), treatment, response assessments and disease progression. Retrospective chart review based on the data dictionaries is continuing at participating sites, with data from 325 CLL and 100 MM patients collected. These data are providing a platform to assess data quality and digital maturity at participating centres. In the next phase of the project, data will be mapped onto the OMOP-CDM at participating hospitals, to generate an Irish platform for Blood Cancer federated research.

7. Standardisation and Quality Control of Irish Lymphoid Blood Cancers Data with the OMOP CDM and eHDPRep

Kluyvert Boakye Duah¹²³, Amanda Kowalczyk¹², Kemdil Anyaoku², Aedin C. Culhane²⁴, Mark Lawler¹²³, Siobhan Glavey²⁵⁶, Ruth Clifford²⁴⁷, Ian M. Overton¹²³

¹ Johnston Cancer Research Centre, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

² eHealth Hub for Cancer, Limerick, Ireland

³ Health Data Research UK, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁴ Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre, Health Research Institute, School of Medicine, University of Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

⁵ Department of Pathology, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, Dublin, Ireland

⁶ Department of Haematology, Beaumont Hospital, Dublin, Ireland

⁷ Department of Haematology, University Hospital Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

Sharing health data significantly improves healthcare and enables biomedical research. Data standardisation with the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) CDM provides a consistent and structured representation, enabling sharing across disparate sites. Landscape analysis provides an understanding of the current state of cancer data, and opportunities for improvement. We focus upon Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia (CLL) and Multiple Myeloma (MM), which affect many people globally with >45,000 and >120,000 annual deaths, respectively.

We present a landscape analysis of cancer data on the island of Ireland, and a workflow to map health data into the OMOP CDM. A cross-sectional study conducted between October 2024 and April 2025 found that none of the eight institutions examined use a CDM such as OMOP. The scope of our core dataset for the mapping was defined with data dictionaries for CLL and MM, produced with clinical oversight. Our initial case study is for 173 patients and 14 fields for CLL. Part of our workflow deploys Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) software; for example 'White Rabbit' screens the input database and 'Rabbit-in-a-Hat' provides an interface to describe the mappings. The eHDPRep R package increased variables completeness to >97% and semantically enriched the UHL data with 144 new metavariables.

The landscape analysis reviewed the diversity in cancer data systems on the island and confirmed a data standardisation gap. We also trailblaze mapping of UHL data to the OMOP CDM, this is an essential step towards all-Island cancer data federation and analysis towards better patient outcomes.

8. Evolutionary Insights into the B7 Immune Checkpoint Family and Their Implications for Tissue-Specific Immunotherapy Response.

Dibyaswarupa Mohanty, Aedin C. Culhane

School of Medicine, University of Limerick, Ireland
Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre, University of Limerick, Ireland

Background: Tissue-specific factors play a critical role in shaping tumour biology and therapeutic response. Large precision oncology trials, such as NCI-MATCH, have demonstrated that identical molecular alterations can result in markedly different drug responses depending on tissue context. Similarly, immune checkpoint inhibitors exhibit highly variable efficacy across tumour types, reflecting poorly understood tissue-dependent immune regulatory mechanisms. This project aims to investigate the genetic, transcriptomic, and evolutionary determinants of tissue-specific therapeutic responses in immune oncology, with a particular focus on the B7 immune checkpoint family (including PD1, CTLA4, and HHLA2) and the contribution of human endogenous retroviral (HERV)-derived elements to immune regulation. We hypothesize that immune genes evolve under strong tissue-specific selective pressures driven by pathogen exposure, microenvironmental constraints, and functional specialization.

Methods: To characterize the evolutionary dynamics of immune checkpoint genes, protein BLAST analyses were performed for all ten human B7 family members against mammalian orthologs. Orthologous protein sequences were identified using Ensembl and retrieved from NCBI. A custom BLAST database was constructed, and high-confidence matches ($\geq 50\%$ sequence identity) were retained, selecting one representative sequence per species. Individual gene alignments were generated using MAFFT and subsequently concatenated into a single multi-gene dataset. Phylogenetic reconstruction was performed using IQ-TREE with automated model selection and branch support estimation. Individual gene trees were also generated to assess gene-specific evolutionary patterns. Future phases incorporate bulk and single-cell transcriptomics and multi-omics integration for predictive modeling of therapy response.

Results: Phylogenetic analysis of the concatenated B7 gene dataset reveals clear patterns of both conservation and diversification across mammalian lineages, reflecting the dynamic evolutionary history of immune checkpoint genes. Several B7 family members show strong conservation consistent with essential immune regulatory roles, while others display greater divergence, suggesting lineage- and potentially tissue-specific adaptations. Individual gene trees further highlight differential evolutionary trajectories within the family. These findings provide foundational evidence that immune checkpoint genes are shaped by heterogeneous selective pressures, supporting the hypothesis that evolutionary history contributes to tissue-dependent immune regulation.

Conclusion: This work establishes an evolutionary framework for understanding tissue-specific behaviour of immune checkpoint genes in cancer. By integrating phylogenetics with future transcriptomic and multi-omics analyses, this project aims to improve mechanistic insight into

Poster Abstracts: All-Island Cancer Data Forum

26th and 27th January 2026, Riddel Hall, Queen's University Belfast

why immunotherapies demonstrate variable efficacy across tumour types. Ultimately, these findings have the potential to enhance predictive models for patient stratification, optimize clinical trial matching, and advance tissue-informed precision immuno-oncology.

Plan Ahead: The next phase of this project will focus on consolidating the evolutionary framework already established and expanding into tissue-specific transcriptomic and regulatory analyses. By integrating evolutionary divergence, gene expression patterns, and regulatory mechanisms, this work will develop a comprehensive tissue-informed model of B7 immune checkpoint regulation. This integrative approach will enable a transition from identifying tissue-specific differences in immune gene behavior to uncovering the regulatory and evolutionary drivers underlying these patterns, with the ultimate goal of improving prediction of immunotherapy responses across cancer types.

9. Estimating the Patient Population in Ireland for Each Molecularly-Guided Oncology Therapy Approved by the European Medicines Agency: A Paediatric Perspective

G. O'Mahoney¹, B. Reardon^{1,2}, C. Haugh³ and A. Culhane¹

¹eHealth-Hub for Cancer, Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre, School of Medicine, University of Limerick

²Dana-Farber Cancer Institute, Boston, MA, USA

³National Cancer Registry Ireland, Cork

Most oncology therapies approved by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) are molecularly targeted and require somatic genomic testing. This study estimates the number of paediatric patients in Ireland potentially eligible for each EMA-approved molecularly guided oncology therapy. EMA-licensed therapies with genetic indications approved for paediatric use were identified. Clinical eligibility was determined using National Cancer Registry Ireland data (2018–2022), applying staging, treatment, and demographic criteria for first-line indications and mortality following tumour-directed treatment for subsequent-line indications. Somatic variant prevalence by cancer type and age group was estimated using AACR GENIE (v18.0-public). Clinical incidence and variant prevalence were combined to estimate eligible patient numbers.

10. Genomic Evidence for Depolyploidization as a Stabilising Force in post-WGD Cancers

Evie M. Smyth¹, Elle Loughrin¹, Aliah Hawari², Christopher Wirth², Maria Jakobsdottir³, David C. Wedge², Máire Ní Leathlobhair¹

¹Smurfit Institute of Genetics, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

²Manchester Cancer Research Centre, The University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom

³The Christabel Pankhurst Institute for Health Technology Research and Innovation, University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom

Whole-genome duplication (WGD) is a common event in cancer evolution, providing adaptive advantages by buffering deleterious mutations and increasing evolvability. However, polyploidy imposes fitness costs by increasing replication stress and inducing genomic instability. One potential resolution is depolyploidization, the reversion to a diploid-like state via loss of duplicated material. The prevalence and dynamics of depolyploidization in cancer evolution remain poorly understood.

We analyse data from the 100,000 Genomes Project to characterise depolyploidization in cancer. We integrate metrics from copy number profiles, subclonal structures and multiplicity-based bimodalities to detect depolyploidized tumours. Simulations using CINner and event timing with GRITIC were used to validate our method. We assessed clinical data to determine the phenotypic consequences of depolyploidization.

Depolyploidization is rare (~6.9% of WGD samples) but enriched in certain tumour types including lung large cell and oesophageal adenocarcinoma suggesting tissue-specific evolutionary constraints. A moderate positive correlation between WGD frequency and depolyploidization prevalence implies that depolyploidization is a post-WGD phenomenon. Depolyploidized tumours are distinct from stable diploids, despite similar ploidy, supporting the notion that they are derived from tetraploid ancestors, not baseline diploid tumours. Importantly, depolyploidized tumours are associated with significantly poorer survival compared to diploid tumours. This framework, combining real tumour genomics with simulations, provides a practical and conceptual basis for detecting tetraploid-to-diploid transitions and understanding their impact on cancer evolution.

11. Concurrent endometrial cancer in patients with an index endometrial hyperplasia diagnosis: a population-based study

Chloe McCoy¹, Helen Coleman¹, Charlene McShane¹, Finian Bannon¹, Omolara Sanni², W Glenn McCluggage³, James Wylie⁴, Declan Quinn⁴, Damien Bennett⁵, Úna McMenamin¹

¹Centre for Public Health, Queen's University, Belfast, United Kingdom

²University of Alberta, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada

³Department of Pathology, Belfast Health and Social Care Trust, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁴Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Antrim Area Hospital, Northern Health and Social Care Trust, Antrim, Antrim, United Kingdom

⁵Northern Ireland Cancer Registry, Belfast, United Kingdom

Background: Concurrent endometrial cancer (EC), defined as EC detected at or within three months of an index endometrial hyperplasia (EH) diagnosis, may lead to suboptimal management, yet population-based evidence remains limited. We aimed to quantify the proportion of concurrent EC among EH patients who later developed EC, and to identify associated factors.

Methods: Patients in the Northern Ireland EH Register (2008–2019) were linked to the Northern Ireland Cancer Registry to identify individuals with diagnoses of both EH and EC. To ensure at least three years of follow-up, EH diagnoses after 2016 were excluded. Logistic regression compared demographic and clinical characteristics between patients with concurrent EC and those with incident EC (diagnosed ≥ 3 months after EH). Models were adjusted for age, deprivation, year of diagnosis, diagnostic method, EH type, and the presence of EH within an endometrial polyp.

Results: Among 221 EH patients who developed EC, 66.5% ($n = 147$) had concurrent EC. Of these, 87.7% had atypical hyperplasia and 11.6% had hyperplasia without atypia. Atypical hyperplasia was associated with higher odds of concurrent EC (adjusted OR 3.71, 95% CI: 1.42–9.68). EH identified within an endometrial polyp was associated with reduced concurrent EC risk in unadjusted analyses, though this was not significant after adjustments.

Conclusions: This first UK population-based assessment of concurrent EC among women with EH demonstrates a high proportion of concurrent diagnoses and supports existing surveillance guidance. Findings highlight the importance of accurate initial EH classification to ensure timely detection of underlying malignancy.

12. Endometrial cancer and prior diagnosis of endometrial hyperplasia: a population-based study

Chloe McCoy¹, Helen Coleman¹, Charlene McShane¹, Finian Bannon¹, Omolara Sanni², W Glenn McCluggage³, Declan Quinn⁴, James Wylie⁴, Anna Gavin⁵, Damien Bennett⁵, Úna McMenamin¹

¹Centre for Public Health, Queen's University, Belfast, United Kingdom

²University of Alberta, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada

³Department of Pathology, Belfast Health and Social Care Trust, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁴Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Antrim Area Hospital, Northern Health and Social Care Trust, Antrim, United Kingdom

⁵Northern Ireland Cancer Registry, Belfast, United Kingdom

Background: Endometrial hyperplasia (EH) is the recognised precursor of endometrioid endometrial cancer (EC), but it is unclear whether a prior EH diagnosis influences EC survival. This study estimated the proportion of EC patients with a prior EH diagnosis in Northern Ireland (NI) and evaluated its association with survival.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective population-based cohort study of all EC cases diagnosed in NI from 2013–2019. EC patients with a prior pathological diagnosis of EH from 2008, and up to three months before their cancer diagnosis, were identified from the NI Cancer Registry. Overall survival was compared between EC patients with and without prior EH using Cox proportional hazards models adjusted for key confounders.

Results: Among 1,771 EC cases, 53 (3.0%) had a previous EH diagnosis. These patients were younger (mean 60.3 vs 65.8 years), more often diagnosed with Stage I disease (96.2% vs 74.9%), and more likely to have Grade 1 tumours (71.7% vs 39.4%). Prior EH was associated with improved unadjusted survival (HR 0.35, 95% CI 0.16–0.79), but this association was no longer evident after adjusting for age, diagnosis year, deprivation, stage, and grade (adjusted HR 1.85, 95% CI 0.76–4.54).

Conclusions: A small proportion of EC patients had a prior EH diagnosis, and those who did presented with more favourable tumour characteristics. Although an apparent survival benefit was observed, this was largely explained by earlier stage disease. These findings suggest that prior EH may not independently improve survival, but can facilitate earlier detection of EC.

13. The incidence of endometrial hyperplasia in Northern Ireland: A population-based study

Lauren McKenna¹, Haydee Jordao¹, Omolara Sanni², Chloe McCoy¹, W Glenn McCluggage³, James Wylie⁴, Declan Quinn⁴, Anna Gavin⁵, Damien Bennett⁵, Helen Coleman⁵, Christopher Cardwell¹, Úna McMenamin¹

¹Centre for Public Health, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

²University of Alberta, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Alberta, Canada

³Department of Pathology, Belfast Health and Social Care Trust, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁴Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Antrim Area Hospital, Northern Health and Social Care Trust, Antrim, United Kingdom

⁵Northern Ireland Cancer Registry, Belfast, United Kingdom

Background: Endometrial hyperplasia (EH) is a recognised precursor to endometrioid endometrial cancer, with progression risk varying by histological subtype. Population-level data on EH incidence are limited. This study estimated the incidence of EH in Northern Ireland (NI) over a 14-year period and examined trends by EH subtype, age, and socioeconomic deprivation.

Methods: We conducted a population-based incidence study using data from the NI Endometrial Hyperplasia Register, including EH cases diagnosed between 2008 and 2022 and classified according to WHO 2014/2020 criteria. Cases with prior or concurrent endometrial cancer were excluded through linkage with the NI Cancer Registry using unique health and care numbers. European age-standardised incidence rates per 100,000 person-years were calculated using hysterectomy-adjusted NI population estimates. Incidence trends were assessed overall and stratified by EH subtype (with and without atypia), age group, and deprivation quintile.

Results: A total of 2,997 EH cases were identified, including 890 cases of atypical EH and 2,085 cases without atypia. Overall EH incidence declined by 7.7%, from 32.3 per 100,000 person-years in 2008 to 29.8 per 100,000 person-years in 2022. Trends differed by EH subtype, with atypical EH incidence increasing by 12.9% over the study period, while incidence of EH without atypia decreased by 22.8%. Incidence patterns varied by socioeconomic status, with a 7% reduction observed among individuals living in the least deprived areas compared with a 50% increase among those in the most deprived areas. Incidence was highest among individuals aged 50–54 years for any EH and EH without atypia, and among those aged 55–59 years for atypical EH.

Conclusions: The incidence of endometrial hyperplasia in Northern Ireland declined over the past 14 years, although opposing trends were observed by EH subtype and socioeconomic status. These findings likely reflect evolving diagnostic and pathological practices, including increased pathological subspecialisation, rather than uniform changes in underlying disease risk.

14. Stage at diagnosis and breast cancer-specific mortality in breast cancer patients treated with antidepressants, anxiolytics, and antipsychotics: A population-based cohort study from Northern Ireland.

Sarah Baxter¹, Charlene M. McShane¹, Stuart A. McIntosh^{1,2}, Damien Bennett^{3,1}, Lynne Lohfeld¹, Daniel R.S. Middleton¹, Gerard Savage³, Deirdre Fitzpatrick³, Joseph Kane^{1,4}, Ann McBrien⁵, David McCallion⁶, Anna Gavin¹, Chris R. Cardwell¹

¹Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

²Belfast City Hospital, Belfast Health and Social Care Trust, Belfast, United Kingdom

³Northern Ireland Cancer Registry, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁴Department of Psychiatry of Old Age, Belfast Health and Social Care Trust, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁵Patient Representative, Northern Ireland, United Kingdom

⁶Patient Representative, England, United Kingdom

Purpose: We examined stage at diagnosis and breast cancer-specific mortality in a cohort of breast cancer patients prescribed medications used for mental health conditions before diagnosis.

Methods: Women newly diagnosed with breast cancer from 2011 to 2021 were identified from the Northern Ireland Cancer Registry. The primary outcome was time to breast cancer-specific mortality up to March 2023. Secondary outcomes included stage at diagnosis. We identified anxiolytic, antidepressant, and antipsychotic prescriptions dispensed in the year before breast cancer diagnosis from the Northern Ireland Enhanced Prescribing Database. Cox regression models were used to calculate adjusted hazard ratios (aHR) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs) for cancer-specific mortality by use of medications.

Results: We included 13,846 women with breast cancer. In the year before breast cancer diagnosis, 31.5% were dispensed antidepressants, 12.7% anxiolytics and 3.5% antipsychotics. The odds of late-stage disease presentation in breast cancer patients dispensed medications for mental health conditions was similar to breast cancer patients not dispensed these medications, but patients dispensed antipsychotics had higher odds of unknown stage. We found no difference in the hazard rate of breast cancer-specific mortality in patients dispensed, versus not dispensed, anxiolytics (aHR=1.06 95%CI 0.93-1.20) a small increase in patients dispensed, versus not dispensed, antidepressants (aHR=1.11 95%CI 1.01-1.23) and a moderate increase in patients dispensed, versus not dispensed, antipsychotics (aHR=1.45 95%CI 1.17-1.81).

Conclusions: Breast cancer patients dispensed medications for mental health conditions were not at higher odds of presenting with late-stage disease, but patients dispensed antidepressants, and especially antipsychotics, had worse breast cancer-specific mortality.

15. House value as an individual socioeconomic indicator for breast cancer survival and late-stage diagnosis: a population-based cohort study from Northern Ireland

Sarah Baxter¹, Charlene M. McShane¹, Stuart A. McIntosh^{1,2}, Damien Bennett^{3,1}, Meenakshi Sharma¹, Lynne Lohfeld¹, Daniel R.S. Middleton¹, Gerard Savage³, Deirdre Fitzpatrick³, Ann McBrien⁴, David McCallion⁵, Anna Gavin¹, Chris R. Cardwell¹

¹Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

²Belfast City Hospital, Belfast Health and Social Care Trust, Belfast, United Kingdom

³Northern Ireland Cancer Registry, Belfast, United Kingdom

⁴Patient Representative, Northern Ireland, United Kingdom

⁵Patient Representative, England, United Kingdom

Purpose: Socio-economic inequalities in breast cancer survival persist in the UK. Area-based deprivation measures may underestimate socio-economic effects by assigning average deprivation levels to all area inhabitants. This study investigated associations between house value (individual-level socio-economic indicator) and area-based deprivation with breast cancer outcomes in Northern Ireland.

Methods: Women diagnosed with breast cancer from 2011 to 2021 were identified using the Northern Ireland Cancer Registry. House value was determined from Valuation and Lands Agency property valuation data, and area-based deprivation was determined from the Northern Ireland Multiple Deprivation Measure. The primary outcome was breast cancer-specific mortality. Secondary outcomes were all-cause mortality and stage at diagnosis. Cox regression models calculated adjusted hazard ratios (HR) and (95%CI) for cancer-specific mortality by house value category and separately for deprivation, adjusting for confounders.

Results: Among 12,766 women with breast cancer, women in the lowest versus highest house value category had a 60% increase in mortality (adjusted HR=1.60 95%CI 1.34, 1.92; per 20 percentile decrease adjusted HR=1.12 95%CI 1.08, 1.16) and were more likely to be diagnosed with stage 4 disease (7.5% versus 4.1%; P<0.001). Women living in the most versus least deprived areas had a 26% increase in mortality (adjusted HR=1.26 95%CI 1.08, 1.47; per 20 percentile decrease adjusted HR=1.05 95%CI 1.01, 1.08) but had no difference in stage 4 disease (5.9% vs 5.0%; P=0.157).

Conclusion: House value demonstrated stronger associations with breast cancer outcomes than area-level deprivation, suggesting it may serve as a more sensitive indicator for monitoring health inequalities in cancer.

16. CRUK Cancer Data Driven Detection (CD3) Programme

Lara Edwards¹, Antonis Antoniou², Sunil Dolwani³, Ashley Akbari⁴, Montse Garcia-Closas⁵

¹Health Data Research UK, London, United Kingdom

²University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom

³Cardiff University, Cardiff, United Kingdom

⁴Swansea University, Swansea, United Kingdom

⁵Institute for Cancer Research, London, United Kingdom

CD3 is a new multidisciplinary and multi-institutional strategic national research programme dedicated to using data to transform our understanding of cancer risk and enable early interception of cancers.

We currently lack a deep understanding of who is most at risk of developing cancer. There is significant scope to more effectively stratify the population based on risk. Increasing volumes of data are being collected and collated on individuals and populations, presenting a timely opportunity to develop methodologies that link and enable access to these datasets; and, through advanced analytical approaches, identify and validate novel risk factors that improve multifactorial cancer risk assessment.

CD3 will:

- Enable access to multimodal data resources following FAIR principles, enriched through novel cancer-related data linkages
- Build UK-wide multidisciplinary expertise and capacity in cancer data science and analytics
- Develop and apply state-of-the-art advanced analytics, including AI and ML based approaches, for identifying novel cancer risk factors and developing and evaluating cancer risk prediction models
- Build multifactorial models to improve our ability to predict cancer risk for asymptomatic and symptomatic populations
- Foster partnerships with patients, the public, practitioners, policy makers, and with key initiatives across the health data science ecosystem to support acceptable and implementable data driven cancer risk prediction and cancer detection in routine front-line healthcare.

This poster provides more information about CD3 UK wide data strategy and partners, scientific aims, objectives and potential impact.

17. ELIXIR-Ireland and Bioconductor: Opportunities for Irish Genomics Research

Maria Doyle, Gavin Farrell, Aedín Culhane

School of Medicine, University of Limerick, Ireland

As Ireland scales up its national genomics infrastructure, alignment with international and European networks is key to maximising impact, including in areas such as cancer genomics and the integration of cancer-related data. Two such initiatives, ELIXIR and Bioconductor, offer complementary strengths: ELIXIR connects life science data resources across Europe - supporting training, interoperability, and shared data and software standards - while Bioconductor provides a robust R-based ecosystem for reproducible genomics data analysis widely used in cancer research.

The ELIXIR-Ireland node, led by the University of Limerick, brings together five national partners and supports strategic areas including cancer genomics, personalised medicine, microbiome science, and the national Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) contributing to the 1+Million Genomes initiative. It connects Irish-developed resources to the broader European ecosystem and ensures that national capabilities contribute to both health-focused and wider bioscience domains.

UL also plays a global leadership role in Bioconductor, leading international grants and projects focused on tool development, infrastructure, and training. This includes coordinating a global Bioconductor training programme and a train-the-trainer network with over 50 instructors, which recently delivered three courses in Africa in collaboration with local partners, reflecting our commitment to inclusive, globally connected capacity building.

We welcome engagement from researchers across Ireland, particularly those working with cancer datasets, who are interested in using or contributing to these initiatives. By aligning national research needs with international infrastructure, we aim to foster a more connected, reproducible, and impactful genomics and cancer data research environment across the island of Ireland.

18. eHealth-Hub for Cancer: A Cancer Data Network on the Island of Ireland eHealth-Hub for Cancer Consortium

David Akwuru^{1,3*}, Kluivert Boakye Duah^{5*}, Arya Soman^{1,4*}, Brendan Reardon^{1,11*}, Ditya Swarupa Mohanty^{1*}, Jeremiah Akintomide^{1,3*}, Abhishek^{1*}, Ethna McFerran⁵, Ruth Clifford^{1,2}, Katie Crowley^{1,3}, Shirin Moghaddam^{1,4}, William Weston⁶, Clare Donohoe¹⁰, Nina Orfali¹⁰, Eva Szegezdi⁷, Siobhan Galvey⁸, Mary Cahill⁹, Amir Jalali¹, Michael Quinn⁵, Ian Overton⁵, Simon McDade⁵, Mark Lawler⁵, Aedin C. Culhane¹

¹Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre, School of Medicine, Health Research Institute, University of Limerick, Ireland

²Department of Haematology, University Hospital Limerick, Limerick, Ireland

³Department of Computer Science & Information Systems, University of Limerick, Ireland

⁴Department of Mathematics and Statistics (MACSI), University of Limerick, Ireland

⁵The Johnston Cancer Research Centre, Queens University Belfast, Northern Ireland

⁶University College Dublin, School of Medicine, Conway Institute Belfield Dublin, Ireland

⁷University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

⁸RCSI, Pathology Department, Smurfit Building, Beaumont Hospital, Dublin, Ireland

⁹Department of Pathology, University College Cork, Cork, Ireland

¹⁰Department of Surgery, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

¹¹Dana-Farber Cancer Institute, Brookline Ave, Boston, MA, USA

*PhD students